

Introduction to

The Supernatural Factors Between Vietnamese And

Western Cultures: From A Literary and Psychological

Perspective

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Abstract

Horror elements or supernatural factors, in general, play a crucial role in the spiritual life of people around the world, largely contributing to the horror genre of storytelling. This type of literary genre stems from adaptation and cultural acculturation, based on the foundation of inheriting and promoting the traditional values, as well as adapting and appropriating other cultures. Through word of mouth, supernatural elements are passed down and recorded into literary works as a means of contemplating different cultural dimensions and the mystery of Nature versus human life. Such factors profoundly impact the cultural consciousness within a community, the historical situation, and the current societal condition. Aspects of various horror and supernatural factors not only satisfy the literary needs and tastes of the readers, but also contribute to shaping the literature and providing a psychological observation into both Vietnamese and Western cultures.

Keywords: *Horror Elements, Horror Stories, Aspects, Cultural Identity, Supernatural Elements*

Introduction

The oldest and strongest human emotion is fear.

— H. P. Lovecraft (1927)

Fear is the emotion that has been instilled in human life for centuries. An emotion that drives humans to create and establish their faiths and religions on Earth (Freud 2024). One fear of the unknown and mysterious forces in Nature, unexplainable yet impersonating a high power, can alter people's minds and decisions to live their lives. Each life-threatening phenomenon is associated with a name, a humanoid or inhumanoid creature possessing supernatural power, and the reasons that humans believe in such beings, which Carl Jung defines as the collective unconscious (1971). As a result, a wide range of archetypal characters, such as gods, demons, monsters, and ghosts, stem from the origin of creation in humans' unconsciousness through folk tales and lore.

Although scientific discoveries have debunked such beings, their legends and tales remain in world literature and art, especially in the religious and cultural aspects of life. One genre that promotes such supernatural factors is fantasy, which branches out into other notable genres, such as science fiction and horror. Many authors have attempted to distinguish and separate horror from similar genres, which have gained popularity in recent years. However, they must steer clear of evoking the feeling of suspense in their audience that genres like true crime and thriller have employed for years. As a result, horror authors encounter difficulties in the supernatural and horror details that can be found in other genres.

Horror, in its simplest form, is a genre that dives deep into the “realistic psychological fears” within a human being by “featuring elements [of the unknown]” (*The Encyclopedia Britannica*, 2014) from a darker side. Though the meaning of ‘horror’ sets the foundation for the horror genre, its connotation varies from one culture to another, expressed in the distinctive plotlines and corresponding elements and symbols. Nevertheless, no matter what culture the horror factors reside in, the characters of horror stem from humans’ “need for suppression if [the horror elements are] interpreted as expressing uncomfortable and disturbing desires which need to be contained” (Strinati, 2000, p. 82). While Western culture treats horror events as separate phenomena or beings outside society, attempting to break the cycle of everyday life, Eastern

culture, specifically Vietnam, weaves such elements into society as a vital part of the daily life and communities of their origin, either collaborating with or disrupting from within. Both perspectives, thus, provide the same psychological picture of people's shared subconsciousness regarding the desire for an opposite force or power to suppress or satisfy such nuisances.

Even though both Eastern and Western literatures, influenced by folk cultures, consist of supernatural and horror elements, the written literature of East Asian cultures (including medieval Vietnam) has recorded horror stories in manuscripts long before Western cultures. On the one hand, the horror genre in Western culture established itself as a standalone genre, gaining popularity since the end of the eighteenth century during the pre-Romantic period with notable writers and stories, such as *Castle of Otranto* (Horace Walpole), *The Tell-Tale Heart* (Edgar Allan Poe), and *The Sandman* (A. Hoffman). Such authors have introduced new themes to the genre, such as the declining psychological mind and pseudoscience. On the other hand, one of the earliest manuscripts regarding daily horror factors is the *Shanhai jing* (*The Classic of Mountains and Seas*), whose earliest version dates back to the 4th century BCE (Bagrow 2009):

Three hundred miles to the south is Mount Fuli, on which there is much gold and jade, and below there are many rocks as sharp as needles. There exists a beast that looks like a fox but has nine tails, nine heads, and tiger claws. The beast is Longdiet (meaning Royal nephew), and its cry is like a newborn baby. A vicious beast that skins and devours people who wander on the mountain.

(*The Classic of Mountains and Seas*)

Illustration of Longdiet. Public Domain

Although the horror genre and its distinctive images are worth studying, many issues related to this subject remain unsatisfactorily resolved. Among them, two important questions deserve more attention: What defines a horror element (?); and how does it incorporate into the literary world and human's perspective of the world (?). They are also the foundation for perceiving such a unique literary genre.

Chapter I: Ghost and Demon

Definition

In folk perception, the body and soul attach and separate from one another depending on different states of life. When a creature dies, the body returns to earth, but the soul still exists and moves on to another world. That form of spiritual phenomenon is commonly known as “ghost” or “demon.” Almost all religions and spiritual traditions around the world mention the existence of ghosts and demons in variations. Some would categorize supernatural creatures and mythical monsters as demons, while others see them as different species. Their images inspire literature and culture around the world since ancient times, from written literature and words of mouth to stories and lore in modern publications like games and movies. Such publications of spirituality are evidence of the spiritual belief as part of the human mind. A rather mysterious phenomenon that still captures the attention of modern people about the invisible thread connecting the dead and the living.

Ghosts and demons are forms of ethereal life in a parallel world or the underworld. They turn to the living, sometimes even participating in the work of the living in a supportive way. In folk beliefs, they can harm people (evil spirits), relay their messages, help people avoid disasters, and bless the living. Therefore, in some cultures, ghosts are worshipped and praised for having supernatural powers like deities. Their existence poses a wide range of spiritual abilities, including possession, which is often associated with shamanic beliefs and practices (Eliade, 2004). Besides possession, other descriptions of supernatural beings interacting with humans for various purposes exist. As a result, human belief in the other world is not only a mythical consciousness in primitive cultures but also a spiritual practice that exists even in the modern world.

In Vietnam

According to Khon Nguyen, the author of a Sino-Vietnamese Dictionary (1960), ghost (*ma*) and demon (*quỷ*) are nouns that refer to supernatural beings; they are also adjectives that refer to someone with a cunning, naughty, and evil nature; they are sometimes adverbs referring to something that harms or intends to harm people in an unacceptable way (p. 572, 764). While the Vietnamese Dictionary of the Institute of Linguistics in Vietnam defines

ghost as “the soul of a dead person” or “the presence of the dead in superstition” (p. 618) and demon as “an imaginary being in Hell (*Diyu*), with a vicious and hideous appearance, usually disturb and harm people, according to legends” (p. 813). However, the definition of ghost and demon in folk culture is more than that. The two words in Vietnamese culture are usually bound together or as a compound noun, referring to a specific supernatural phenomenon.

In Vietnamese folklore, ghosts are often described as a human form, often associated with specific colors like “silver white”, ethereal states such as “dim shadow”, “half transparent”, “like fog”, or “black pile”, and hair that is “disheveled” or “unkempted.” In short, ghosts are shadows, the souls of the deceased, which are challenging to determine their shapes. They often float or fly. Their feet do not touch the ground. They do not cast shadows, and they come and go like a breeze. Ghosts do not have a living body like humans. Vietnamese people believe that the society of ghosts is in the Underworld, and the place where ghosts live is their graves (*idioms*: The living live in their house, the dead their graves; Gods reside in Banyan trees, while ghosts in red silk-cotton trees).

Similar to how Western fairies have their forts or hills, ghosts in Vietnamese belief have their own space, like “ a big red silk-cotton tree with lush canopy. At night, the ghosts gather to discuss worldly matters,” and as ghosts, “when dawn breaks, [they] scatter in the darkness to other directions” (Cung Khanh, 1944). However, the boundary between the ghost world and the human world is also translucent and vague, as “too white for one’s grasp to keep,/ When the fog thickens, blurring one’s sight” (Han, 1938, ll. 10-1). Ghosts can also linger in dark, deserted places that are related to when they were alive. However, they can become demons either by gaining enough hatred or lingering long enough to become sentient.

Red Silk-Cotton Tree

Banyan Tree

Vietnamese folklore also defines that only people who have a “fate” with a spirit can see other ghosts, or people with special abilities, like psychics, can “communicate” with ghosts. Ghosts can know everything that the living think, can learn what has happened, is happening and will happen, or have the ability to affect the body and speech of the living such as spirit possession, involving the senses of the living by leading them to get lost in the parallel world through bushes or inciting them to eat mud as if they were eating bread. Ghosts in Vietnamese culture can also affect the physical world by creating noises, shaking trees, and moving tables and chairs, which is similar to the Western belief of their supernatural abilities.

In Vietnamese Taoism, a folk culture that branched from Chinese Taoism, ghosts do not have shadows and are not reflected in mirrors. Most ghosts are afraid of sunlight and gods. Charms and signs such as the Bagua, the cross, dog blood, garlic, onions, mulberry trees, fishtail palms, lime powder, and cactus are said to ward off ghosts. However, no evidence provides a clear explanation for why ghosts are afraid of those things.

Demons, in contrast, have superior power. Although demons are more real than ghosts, people are often more afraid of ghosts than demons due to their ambiguity. Their society is also in the Underworld. Unlike ghosts, they can roam freely in the living world, without a home. As a result, the definition of demon in Vietnamese culture shares the same grotesque qualities as that in Western culture, as seen in Dante’s *Inferno* (2003):

Ah, he was surely barbarous to see!
And how relentless seemed to me his acts!
His wings were open, and his feet were lithe;
...
Across his shoulder, which was sharp and high,
If you are just as keen as usual,
Can’t you see how those demons grind their teeth?
Their brows are menacing, they promise trouble.”

(Canto XXI)

Thus, ‘ghost’ and ‘demon’ in Vietnamese culture refer to a spiritual phenomenon, being passed down from generation to generation, with many different species. Both are considered manifestations of the living, the dead, animals, plants, and old objects, appearing in strange, ferocious, or harmless shapes, mainly to harass and harm human society. In contrast, besides their well-known nature of harming or tricking the living, they can show certain traits of humanity in some folktales and stories. They can enter dreams or transform into the living. In *The God Who Protects The Land* (1300s), the ghost of a young lady comes in his dream, "is the spirit of the land of the South, trapped in a piece of wood", wishing to aid the king in his battle against the Champa invaders (Tran The Phap, 2011, p. 92). Another story is about *Tam and Tu*, with four coffin-carrying demons, who usually appear at three in the morning, strangling strangers who wander into their cave. They boast about secret places for gold, silver, and gems, and whoever gets them will be rich (Nguyen Dong Chi, 2000, p.1674). Thus, demons and ghosts can come into contact with the living without any evil intention. They harbor a desire to express their feelings to the living or to demonstrate their supernatural abilities, knowledge, or to seek human values.

In Western cultures

According to the Merriam-Webster Dictionary, ‘ghost’ is “a disembodied soul” that resides in another world, invisible to the living. They can be in human form, a spirit, or a demon (n.d). Thus, ‘demon’ is seen as an “evil spirit” or a force that possesses supernatural power in the form of what is between “that of a god and that of a human being” (n.d). Both ghosts and demons are supernatural beings, solely related to their religious origins, and act against Christianity-based religions, such as Christianity and Islam.

Following the teachings of the prophet Abraham, demons are the fallen angels, with the first being the infamous Lucifer. Many believe that the fall of Lucifer happened on the sixth day, as he was mentioned in the book of Ezekiel, standing “ in Eden, the garden of God” (Ezekiel 28). As Eden was not created until the sixth day, the Fall of Lucifer would largely happen on that day before God took a rest on the seventh. Lucifer rebelled with one-third of the other angels to gain domination over God. The rebellion was defeated by the good angels, led by Michael. After that, Lucifer and the rebel angels were expelled from heaven. They have been residing in hell since. The Bible also indicates several instances of possession (Carroll &

Prickett, 2008), in which biblical demons offer humans superhuman strength in exchange for a price, causing permanent damage to their physical and mental states, but often a takeover of their bodies. Similar to other religions, such possessions carry different meanings and implications for actual events and illness.

Western cultures define ghosts and demons as separate beings with different motivations and powers, unlike the intertwined concept between the two in Vietnam. Ghosts have the desire for revenge, as seen in Shakespeare's *Hamlet* (2012), through the ghost of old Hamlet lingering on the top of the castle. They can also have a message to deliver (Act I, Scene V), like the spirits of Christmas in Charles Dickens's *A Christmas Carol* (1843). Thus, their intentions are good or evil, but more on the selfish side. On the other hand, demons need to possess the living for their devious acts and intentions to bring their real bodies over from Hell. Since demons in Western cultures reside in Hell and they need to possess a living to enter the real world, their interactions with the living can be limited to a point that researchers see demonic possession as a psychological disease. According to Perrotta (2019), demonic possession is an extreme case of a psychopathological state in which a person is taken over by their beliefs. Thus, Western cultures delve into the study of psychology on such beliefs, uncovering the discovery of humans' unconsciousness, where the origins of horror elements lie, for better explanations.

Ghosts in Western culture also have a place to return, such as the "sick-box" (Saunders, 2017). Similar to Vietnamese belief, stones set at the burial place or the dead anniversary for "ten types of sentient beings" (Nguyen, n.d.), are the desire from the living to share and comfort the dead. Tran Ngoc Them, a cultural researcher, states that "death means the body changes from a dynamic to a static state, so according to the philosophy of yin and yang, the soul goes from the Yang realm to the Yin realm, which is the other world" (2001). The belief that the dead return to the ancestral place and often come back to visit and bless their descendants is unconsciously shared among cultures (e.g., A deceased family relative is watching over their loved ones) as the basis for ancestor worship in people's lives. Among Vietnamese people and other Southeast Asian ethnic groups, such beliefs have become the foundation (Ancestral Religion) for their cultures. Even families who are atheists or Christians dedicate an altar for their ancestors in their homes.

Regardless of the culture, horror images as well as supernatural elements in stories and folk tales reflect the beliefs of not only ancient times but also the modern era. However, some believe that ghosts and demons are unexplained natural phenomena due to the fragile mind fabricating using recognizable “patterns” from “ambiguous stimuli” (Hupp, 2025) as a response within humans’ imagination. Humans often attribute disasters and unusual phenomena in political, cultural, and social life to monstrous symbols. If people with authority speak up to eradicate such spiritual factors, they will naturally disappear over time, as seen throughout history from the spread of Christianity to the disappearances of folk cultures.

In short, ghosts and demons are products of preserving the naive and simple imagination of human beings. The concept of totems, human-heavenly induction, and mythical thinking always exists even today. Although supernatural forces are a matter of belief, their attractiveness has been studied by many, providing distinctive perspectives on their definitions. The appearance of such symbols is a warning to the ruling power and daily life. The images of horror are closely related to the existing difficulties, horror, and fear of what is not perceived in life. Whether the supernatural is real or not, they are the most common material in literature and art. By fearing such forces, people can deeply perceive their own lives and the lives of others.

Chapter II: Horror Elements in Vietnamese and Western Literature

The Horror Genre in Literature

Horror is a familiar concept in literary research. However, from the sources that are the tools of research activities in this field, none have provided a convincing definition. Although a well-known literary genre, discussed by experts, the concept of ‘horror story’ is underdeveloped. Therefore, the need to redefine the horror genre is a necessity.

The use of ‘horror story’ in some modern literary research works often varies. One major problem is that the term is also under other genre labels, with or without equivalent meanings, such as legends, fan fiction, fantasy tales, thrillers, war stories, and ghost stories, borrowing the same storyline with added horror elements. For example, the plot of Bram Stoker’s *Dracula* (1897) is about a group of hunters who go against a rampaging monster that has been harming people’s lives for decades, or the story of Stephen King’s *The Shining* (1977) as a psychological relief of the author from his alcoholism and the fear of his violence against his family (Zbořil 2013), portrayed through the shattered family of a gifted child. In essence, without the horror elements, the plotline of a horror story is the same as other genres, but with an eerie narrative.

What makes horror stories as they are is, first, their preferred setting of a strange, bizarre, and psychologically dangerous location, such as a sacred place, a deep forest, a high mountain, an isolated mansion, or a haunted town. However, such settings are known for their local legends of a potential horror story. As a result, people would categorize the horror story as a legend or an urban myth. In other words, horror stories first started as a legend or myth and, with certain horror factors to escalate the stories, became what they are by constantly instilling fear of the unknown in their audience (Lovecraft 1927, pp. 161-2). That fear of horror stems from the collective instinctual intuition, varying from one culture to the next, as a way to define existence that the culture prefers to avoid or accept. For instance, in Mexican and Latin American folklore, La Llorona is a weeping woman who drowns her children and is condemned to hold that grief for her children for eternity. Throughout the years, the tale of La Llorona has been known as a horror story that parents would retell the myth to scare misbehaved children or to keep them away from any bodies of water (Lasky 2023). Each retold version of the tale has the potential to

include elements that are convenient for parents to instill fear in their children based on different circumstances. Eventually, the story evolves into what the horror tale of La Llorona is today.

In contrast, a potential horror story can fall into a different genre because of the added elements that are opposite to the horror or serve as a resolution to the story. In Inuit mythology, the Sea God, Sedna, who gives birth to six human-dog hybrid children, was killed by her father after he cut off all her fingers and fed her to the sea creatures. Her tale becomes a legend due to the following divine factors: when her cut fingers can give birth to sea creatures, and her hair becomes the sea waves that provide them a nest. If the events that followed were similar to the tale of La Llorona, then Sedna could have become the Inuit version of “The Weeping Woman.” Another example is the tale of Beowulf, who slays Grendel and Grendel’s mother and becomes the hero of King Hygelac’s court. If Grendel kills Beowulf or no instance of him coming to aid King Hygelac, the tale would likely be a candidate for a horror story rather than an epic today.

Although methods of identification are available, many authors assume that horror is a work about the unusual and the bizarre, specializing in evoking extreme negative emotions, such as anxiety, suspense, and fear, in the readers. Thus, the mentioned categories and genres that accept horror reveal the nature and characteristics of the ‘horror story’ in a sense. However, on closer consideration of such categories and genres, the inadequacy and discrepancy between them and the ‘horror story’ pose a problem in defining the horror genre. As the classification only emphasizes the superior image of a story, such categories for the ‘horror story’ are loose and unreasonable by being excessive (comprehensive) or inadequate (one-sided). Nevertheless, any scientific concept is ultimately only a name, a way of identifying subjects. If the same research subject encompasses multiple terms, researchers must consider a more specific and well-defined definition or category. The key issue here is not the name but the connotation of the concept ‘horror story.’

From a nominalistic approach, as horror stories are about unusual and terrifying phenomena, comparing them to other literary genres that use the same details as material or expression methods, the differences are difficult to determine. However, distinguishing ‘horror story’ throughout the history of world literature is even more challenging, as the horror genre has only become a separate genre since the eighteenth century. If researchers only rely on the genre name, “horror”, they cannot recognize the so-called key characteristics of horror stories. On the one

hand, horror elements stem from the human psychological state, being vague due to the subjectivity and emotions they evoke. Such characteristics are embedded in multiple texts in world literature since ancient times. Therefore, the answer to the question: what defines the horror elements (?), will require extensive research rather than a summarization with a few lines.

On the other hand, to avoid being excessive or inadequate, a more diverse and flexible approach is preferable in analyzing the horror elements within a story. Such outstanding and recognizable features of a potential horror story must also take into account the fusion of factors that are opposites, such as between traditional and modern literature or Eastern versus Western cultures, which are expressed in each text. That opposition is implied in the archetypal images that originate from artistic form, ideological contexts, and contents regarding the consciousness of the times, historical and social imprints, and cultural beliefs. As a result, such factors create the aspects and differences between Vietnamese and Western horror literature.

In Vietnamese Literature

In Vietnam, the genre of fantasy and magical literature with elements of strangeness and horror has appeared for a long time, in large numbers and diverse forms. However, literary texts defined as ‘horror stories’ only appeared at the beginning of the 20th century. The word ‘horror’ is originally related to a book titled *Three Horror Stories* (1930) by The Lu, comprising three short stories: ‘A Terrible Tale,’ ‘Howling At Night,’ and ‘Whisperings.’ In his stories, The Lu defined a better concept of the horror genre in Vietnam. Although The Lu did not declare, theorize, or make any announcements, his stories played a suggestive role, opening a new approach to storytelling in modern Vietnamese literature. After *Three Horror Stories*, the number of published horror stories by different writers of the same period received a sharp increase. The development of Vietnamese literature, shaped by horror elements and unified artistic styles, has become a trend, defining a unique subgenre of horror in modern literature.

However, in Vietnamese horror stories, the basic devices of traditional prose have been transformed to adapt to the horror genre, creating what the Vietnamese call *hồn* (hun), *via* (po), and the ‘spirit’ of the political and social influences resulting from the genre. That ‘spirit’ reshapes the familiar horror images in traditional literature to be fundamentally distinctive in Vietnamese horror stories. Those elements become “the opposite of the supernatural,” which is the difference between the abnormal, “expressed in an imaginary, artificial, and unbelievable

world” in ancient and medieval texts, and the horror for “trying to point out the surprises of our world” in horror stories (X. Dareos, as cited in Bang G. 1992, p. 6). Therefore, the foundation of Vietnamese horror stories in their early stages, at a glance, is nothing more than the common motifs that often appear in medieval literature, like myths and legends. For example, the story of a miscarriage mother who cursed the descendants of the villagers for three generations, using human skull wine as revenge for exile due to a prophecy in “Tet in the Village of Hell,” or the story of a medieval district magistrater solving the case of a traveler who takes shelter in an abandoned temple on a rainy night and encounter a demon disguised as himself to trick the villagers in the ‘Whisperings.’

The exclusive feature of Vietnamese horror stories that sets them apart from medieval literature lies in the fusion of contrasting images and symbols (between traditional and modern literature, or East and West), which is revealed through signs belonging to the artistic form (character motifs, events, narrative methods/techniques, etc.), the ideological aspects, and contents of the works such as the consciousness of the current era, social imprints, and cultural perspectives. Modern Vietnamese horror stories, like Western literature, comprise short stories, novellas, and novels. In contrast to Western literature, the evolution of Vietnamese horror stories took place in only two major stages. The first stage, years before the mid-20th century (assuming 1954 as the benchmark), was an early form of folktales and legends. The second stage was that, since 1954, Western culture, especially French literature, gradually exposed the young intellectual writers and authors to new qualitative changes to their work.

However, the influences of Western writers are merely a basis. Vietnamese horror writers create their settings and characters using the materials of their time to reflect the problems of life and a strong national identity. The social issues they reflect carry exclusive national and traditional cultural origins. The stories develop according to different principles with a distinctive character set. In a sense, the introduction of a new culture allows modern Vietnamese writers to escape the inertia of tradition and experiment with a new subgenre of horror stories that can attract their readers while still retaining national literary identity.

In Western Literature

In Western cultures, especially in European and American countries, ‘horror’ is a term specifying a literary genre that is diverse in style, rich in quantity, and marked by a clear

historical trajectory through classic works, such as *The Metamorphosis* by Kafka, *The Sandman* by Hoffmann, "*The Devil in the Belfry*" by Edgar Allan Poe, or *Doctor Jekyll and Mr. Hyde* by Robert Louis Stevenson. In other words, the minimum criteria of horror stories are defined by key functional aspects, genres, and the archetypal images within horror stories, associated with dark, unsettling, and psychological features. Although the idea of horror in both cultures circulates the relationship between the living and the supernatural, Western authors often set their stories in intense situations, associating them with gruesome images of hatred and violence. The living are brutally depicted as weaklings struggling to survive forces beyond their control, such as ghosts and creatures of the night, which often leads to tragic deaths. Their horror stories, in a sense, focus on the terror and horrific constituents of the unknown.

The evolution of horror tales in Western literature can be traced back to their early forms as folktales and legends imbued with horror elements. Such stories are passed through generations using distinctive methods, which are similar across cultures. In the early civilizations, Western cultures witnessed a rise of epics and legends depicting the themes of death and the supernatural through works such as Homer's *Iliad and Odyssey*, mentioning Odysseus traveling to the Underworld, or the epic tale of *Gilgamesh*, narrating a journey through the unknown and the impending death awaiting the protagonists.

When Christianity played a more significant role in daily life during the medieval era, the Western world experienced a rise in enriched horror themes, reflecting people's concern about sins and redemption. For instance, Shakespeare's *Hamlet* (2012) offers a psychological descent into chaos and karmic debt that begins with the echo of revenge from the wandering soul of the late king. Not until the 18th and 19th centuries did the horror genre become official as the Gothic novel (Marriott 2023), setting the first cornerstone for Western horror. The heavily symbolic and rational short stories of horror during the Gothic era, from Edgar Poe and other Western writers, are different from the innocent and folk-friendly quality of horror in Asia. However, their horror stories still had a great influence on Vietnamese writers in the early 20th century and on some later authors of the then-nascent modern prose in Vietnam. Another major turning point for the genre was when writers began experimenting with fear stemming from man's internal psychological conflicts and the "uncanny" (Freud 2024), allowing subgenres like Psychological Horror and Lovecraftian Horror to become the foundation for modern horror experience in Western cultures.

Chapter III: The Psychology behind Supernatural Belief

Although Western and Eastern horror stories both exploit the fear within human beings, the fear that Eastern authors often depict is related to the human conscience, which rarely causes physical consequences due to hatred or hostility. Unlike the West, Eastern culture, since ancient times, has not distinguished between the yin and yang worlds. The living world (Yang) is only a temporary world or a place of exile, while the supernatural or parallel worlds (Yin) are the eternal destinations for all beings. Therefore, the dead always remain in the hearts of the living, maintaining communication. They are not only in a close-knit relationship, but also capable of a vast array of feelings and even deep affection.

The Uncanny

Regardless of culture, the images of horror or supernatural in horror stories reflect beliefs within a community, a product of preserving the naive and the imagination of a certain historical period. The concept of sacred totems, divine induction, and mythical forces has been of both the Vietnamese people and the world since ancient times. People often see natural disasters and unusual phenomena in political, cultural, and social life as supernatural forces, which serve as warnings to their rulers and their lives. Such images are, thus, related to the existing difficulties, horror, and fear of the unknown in life that stem from the unconscious.

According to Sigmund Freud in his work, *The Unconscious* (2005), the unconscious stores all past events, impressions, and memories of humans. In other words, the unconscious stores humans' feelings or memories acquired after a series of events, and even unfulfilled desires. Freud began his research process by focusing on analyzing the characteristics of unconscious psychological processes taking place deep within the human psyche. He identified the ego (consciousness) as the subject of cognition, and mental reality (unconsciousness) as the object of cognition. The cognitive process must understand the mechanism of transition from the unconscious realm (specifically, the mental activities of the unconscious) to the conscious realm of the ego, thereby clarifying the content of the unconscious.

Figure. Sigmund Freud (2005), Demographics of the Iceberg Theory (digital), designed by Thai Huynh

As a result, Freud’s psychoanalysis focuses on the study of the mental entity, which he defined as “the uncanny... belongs to the realm of the frightening, of what evokes fear and dread” (2003, p. 123) or the inner world of human beings. He explained that the unconscious plays a central role in defining ‘the uncanny’ as an element in the natural structure of human existence. From a broader perspective, any supernatural elements, from gods and demons to ghosts and mythical creatures, are the products of the unconscious that defines the nature of man. He further emphasized that the unconscious determines specific mental activities, and the conscious is only

the small part that enacts such activities (2009, p. 13). In other words, the ways people perceive the supernatural forces are closely related to the unconscious, taking place on the unconscious background and being motivated by instinctive impulses. Therefore, in works of horror, authors must develop an objective view of the supernatural elements in all aspects of life without being influenced by their narrow unconscious through certain sacred images or symbols that their audience can recognize and share the same perspective with them.

Along with Freud, Jung (1963) and Fromm (1960) also recognized ‘the uncanny’ as a field of human spiritual life. ‘The uncanny’ is not outside the scope of scientific research, but is also the subject of science. Through their works, ‘the uncanny,’ together with science and religion, will lead humanity to a harmonious development of all biological, social, psychological, and spiritual challenges. While Freud explained human spirituality from the origin of Totemism (1990) and Jung delved deeper into the realm of human dreams, Fromm’s theories of the development of true individuality provide a scientific perspective on supernatural phenomena.

In contrast, their works also identify ‘the uncanny’ as an existence that blurs the boundary between imagination and reality. Hoffman’s *The Sandman* (1816) is perhaps Freud’s notable example of such existence, reflecting a dreadful desire through the Sandman, a supernatural being, as a means to navigate the subject’s reality. Therefore, the subject is torn between his imagination and reality, drowning in the effect of ‘the uncanny.’ Such an effect, as Freud stated, is “often arises when the boundary between fantasy and reality is blurred, when we are faced with the reality of something that we have until now considered imaginary, when a symbol takes on the full function and significance of what it symbolizes” (2003, p. 150), resulting in so often the appearances of horror elements. As the products of supernatural beliefs blend with reality, humans find themselves vulnerable to the unknown.

Dreams

Dreams are a phenomenon of seeing people or things appear as real as the living world. They take on a myriad of forms, appearing in situations that a person allows his unconscious to take control in sleep, daydream, delusion, hallucination, etc. In some cultures, dreams are epiphanies or messengers from both gods and demons. Dreams are also a device for “primitive people” to “communicate with gods or souls from another world” (Tylor, p. 130), and through contemplation of dreams, people form the concept of the soul, which they use to explain the situations and actions committed by their dreams (Engels 1996). Thus, dreams are the product of spiritual influences that originate from the unconscious as gateways of communication between reality and the supernatural world. Therefore, dreams are a product as real as reality. When a person dreams, each dream results from the physiological and psychological state of both mind and body. They are visions or warnings that foretell consequences or events that may happen accurately in reality. For example, a person learning a foreign language dreams about speaking that language fluently, interpreted as a premonition of the future self. Or the dream of August Kekulé, the father of benzene, dreamt about six snakes biting their tails, resulting in the discovery of benzene’s structure. Therefore, dreams, whether confused, have their causes and effects. In short, not until people dream can they fill the map of reality with more details.

According to Freud (1976a) and Jung (1984), dreams carry specific messages that the subconscious wants to deliver to the conscious mind from the unconscious realm. Dreams, to them, are not “a meaningless product of disturbed psychological activity,” but are “a personal psychological achievement of the dreamer” and the result of “the opposition between the awakened ego and the suppressed unconscious” (Freud 1976a, pp. 99-147). After distinguishing between dream manifestation and latent, Freud stated that “often the thoughts in the most recent dream are the ones that most easily attract [people] because of their unusual appearance. They are expressed not in the everyday language in which we are accustomed to thinking, but in a symbolic language full of comparisons, metaphors, and rich in imagery like the language of poetry” (1976a, pp. 56,72). He further provided the words of Franz Schubert, an Austrian composer, that “dreams are a liberation of the spirit from the power of external nature, and a freeing of the soul from the bonds of the senses” (Schubert 1814, as cited in Freud 2001, p. 3).

Before the works of Freud, dreams, since ancient times, were desires and callings of the subconscious mind for Truth, Goodness, and Beauty.

For Buddhism, a major religion in Vietnam, certain daily activities can increase man's chances of experiencing certain supernatural factors in their dreams, and the suffering and happiness of dreams are real to the people (Patton 2018). Nietzsche (1967) believes that "to be at all able to dream with this inner joy... we must have completely forgotten the day and its terrible obtrusiveness" (p. 20). In other words, a person's psychological and physical states cause dreams to happen. For example, practicing good deeds and self-restraint can lead to positive dreams, whereas causing evil deeds and self-harm can result in nightmares. In Christianity, God initiates the dreams as a means to relay his messages to his followers (Adderley, 2023), as in his appearance in Abraham's dream for promises of descendants and land to thrive (Genesis 15) or Jacob's meeting with God for guidance on his journey through a symbolic ladder to Heaven in his dream (Genesis 28). Similar to Christianity in some aspects, Spiritualism defines dreams as a premonition, a secret teaching of the gods, or a warning that the uncanny deliver in the form of good dreams and nightmares. While in folklore (ancestral religion for Vietnamese), dreams are not only a basic form of spiritual communication between humans and gods and demons, but also a sign from heaven or a Fate that supernatural forces preside over mortals. Through dreams, people can meet the dead (Nietzsche 2023) or contemplate and predict what will happen in response to their dreams.

Dreams are both bridges and premonitions between the living and the unknown in horror stories. The inspiration of dreams is related to various daily activities, such as meeting deceased relatives, expressing a love desire unfulfilled, meeting beautiful people, seeing gods, and the obsession with Fate (Jung 1966). Regardless of culture, people believe that the worlds of gods and demons exist in parallel to the real world and that these worlds share a spiritual communication. In *The Serpent of the Ma Family* by Lan Khai (2016), a woman met the black serpent that she was raising, in a half-human, half-snake form, crying in her dream: "Mother, save me, your son. At the river, where I reside, a white serpent from another land invades. Tomorrow at noon, we will have a territorial fight. If I lose, I will either die or be chased away. You and I will be separated forever. Mother, if you love me, please bring a knife to our fight tomorrow. When you see a white lump floating up near the riverbank, chop it dead."

Dreams help people contact and perceive desires, omens, and Heavenly Secrets (Fate) that they seek. In *The Tale of Kieu* by Nguyen Du (1987), Kieu dreamed of meeting Dam Tien, a talented songstress who died young, as a sign that her life would be the same. Leaning against the sill, Kiêu was slumbering./Out of nowhere she saw appear a damsel,/A little girl, graceful and impeccable./Face stamped with dew and body shrouded in snow,/She moved round, her feet like two lotus flowers./With joy, Kiêu went out to welcome and asked her:/"Are you coming astray from the fairy land?"/She said: "Those of the same mood share sympathy,/We met each other this afternoon, didn't we?... You had an empathic heart to think of me,/And stooped to write priceless words at my retreat./I reported all of them to the league chief,/Who said your name was also in the Book of Doom./As we see, that's the law of cause and effect,/We're not strangers but same boat's passengers./A sudden strong wind snapped the blind from nowhere,/Kiêu awoke and knew she'd just had a nightmare (ll. 185-214). The Fate of each person seems to have been arranged, and only through dreams are people allowed to receive a sign of their Fates.

Dreams are the moments when the living have a glimpse of something divine. Adam's dreams of his muse, the Leannan Si in the *Muse* (2017) by Jaume Balagueró or *La Dama Numero Trece* (2003) by José Carlos Somoza, are a predestined encounter of an artist searching for beauty. The mythical creature, the Irish Muse, appears in his dreams and hallucinations as an embodiment of divine perfection, inspiring his works with a new emotional level in exchange for his love. As absolute beauty is difficult to achieve in the real world, people can only turn to the uncanny through dreams. Dreams also help the dead remind the living of their past deeds and wishes. Frankenstein's effort in Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein* (2021) to turn his dream into reality, driving him to madness, is a mirror that reflects Shelley's dream of "the spectre," the novel itself, that "had haunted [her] midnight pillow" (p. 3). Dreams are human premonitions that cannot be seen or guessed, signaling phenomena that have happened or will happen, such as love. In *The Ghost Bride* (2014) by Yangsze Choo, Li Lan is married off to the deceased Lim Tian-ching, which triggers a series of dreams as a bridge for the ghost to meet his soon-to-be bride. As each dream passes, Li Lan grows more anxious and frightened as the ghost's desire blurs the line between the two worlds. She must seek help from her nursemaid to cut the red thread that bound her with that spiritual attachment.

To Freud, dreams are understood as mental activities and are a fiction from the imagination, attempting to escape from reality. When moral values are threatened, humans turn to the spiritual world as a solution for “freedom” and “conscience” from the “spiritual beings” (Erenchinova, Evgeniia, & Proudchenko, 2018). The need to delve deeper into human individuality makes man's essence the focus across genres of world literature. By utilizing different forms of dreams, horror writers express the liberation of the individual ego and the desire for human survival in their horror stories. Dreams and supernatural factors, as well as their products, are both a spiritual expression of humans and a concern for humanity. In essence, dreams create a world with gods and ghosts to convey messages about life and satisfy human spiritual desires — A form of spiritual connection between humans, gods, and demons.

Dreams are considered a magical cultural phenomenon that is both tangible and intangible, closely related to real life and human psychological and spiritual activities, from which they pull their materials (Freud 1976, pp. 43-4, 172-3). Therefore, dreams and their inspirations may be real to one person but not to another. Writers, in general, have explored deeper into their inner selves, stimulated their imagination, and released that spiritual energy to expand the supernatural world through both divine and horror elements. Through works that feature dreams, visions, and nightmares, horror stories convey disturbing life philosophies and the sense of survival that helps people understand their humanity. However, the supernatural factors continue to exist in the consciousness as dreams “can only disappear as long as people do not turn to a world outside of ours ... The part of human life that is developing and extending” (Ta, p. 90). As a result, dreams haunt reality. They are nightmares for people who carry guilt for their evil deeds, and overall, as the torment of conscience for the living through their sublime and horrid products.

Critical Synopsis

Wherever the supernatural factors originate, the relationship between culture and literature in recording them is inseparable. In literature, spiritual elements, in general, and horror elements in particular, exist as constituents. They emerge in folktales under the forms of myths, fairy tales, and fables, associated with legends in medieval prose. Such stories of different supernatural forces capture the various forms of the uncanny (dreams, spirit calling, omens, ghosts, and reincarnation) by expressing people's sacred belief, reverence, and admiration for those forces. Although the horror genre has only been officially recognized recently, related works demonstrate the shared features of spirituality across traditions of different cultures and profound thinking, in studying the spiritual life in the modern world. As a result, short stories and novels with spiritual elements are crucial in preserving the core cultural values of humanity. Delving deeper into the soul with spiritual imprints is a voice that sympathizes with human desires, aspirations, and dreams. The approaches to literature from the perspective of culture, in general, and spiritual life in particular, have kept legends, folktales, and horror stories alive through generations.

By exposing themselves to spiritual elements, writers submerge themselves in human consciousness. A world that is abstract and mysterious, but familiar to human beings, containing all the thoughts and emotions of people about the collapse of traditional values in the face of cultural exchange, human fate, happiness, and contemplations about life and death. Readers can learn about their national culture through customs and rituals expressed in the ways of thinking and aesthetic perceptions presented in supernatural and horror literary works. The supernatural in folk tales and the fantasy in medieval stories, intertwined between reality and fiction, have helped record human issues and perspectives across the ages. Through borrowed elements from the supernatural world, horror and fantasy writers can express their thoughts on human affairs and generalize the subtle and daily problems in current society, proving their ability to flexibly inherit the traditional quintessence of their nation and the world.

Conclusion

Whether ghosts and demons are real or not depends on people's beliefs rather than a solidified answer or research. However, they have appeared in various literary works and methods around the world, from gossip to written literature, to relay a story or spiritual phenomenon that human beings cannot explain. As a result, with their unique narratives, each fantasy and horror work demonstrates great achievements in both content and aesthetic perspective. The supernatural elements help writers to develop their imagination in the creative process, satisfying the spiritual needs in every human soul. Belief in supernatural forces (God, Buddha, Saints, and even demons) and the custom of worshipping ghosts and ancestors draw readers into the fantasy yet horrific world of each story. A world of profound characters (ghosts, superhumans, and mysterious creatures) with sacred and mysterious space and time, contributing to a unique language system that possesses a great haunting power to the readers.

In essence, the relationship between literature and culture is symbiotic. Supernatural elements with psychological and cultural effects on the human subconscious are the premise for modern literature. In addition to the endogenous power of traditional literature, the absorption of fantasy and horror, along with contemporary innovations, creative methods, and approaches to spiritual reality, created works full of color, horrid yet fascinating, as a testament to the appeal of profound forces in literature. As a great tradition, both hidden and visible, is behind each genre of literature, worldwide stories about legends and horror forces carry the mission of preserving culture on the journey back to the roots of national culture.

When human society continues to evolve, so does the world of supernatural beings, reflected in the modern images of ghosts and demons in contemporary works. The diversity of supernatural beings is no longer limited to popular forms, such as vampires or imps, but rather transforms into an artistic image that mimics the boundless imagination of the modern human mind. Therefore, the world of human spirituality in literature is boundless. No matter how much research is presented, the knowledge of supernatural representation around the world is merely the tip of an iceberg in studying and explaining the spiritual elements from different perspectives in literature and psychology, serving as the foundation for a better understanding of the supernatural.

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